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Mapping of Former Strategies and Future Needs for Regulatory Prevention of Skin Sensitization: Cosmetic Products

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ABSTRACT

Contact allergy related to use of cosmetic products remains a considerable problem in the European Union population. The objectives of this study were to identify pitfalls in EU risk assessment methodologies and regulation(s) for cosmetic products and identify areas of potential improvements in future regulatory strategies. Two significant contact allergens, methylisothiazolinone and hydroxyisohexyl 3-cyclohexene carboxaldehyde, were investigated as examples. Other contact allergens were used to provide additional context. Opinions from the European Commission's scientific committees and regulatory documents were analysed to identify methodologies, processes and results in terms of preventive effects. The analysis revealed key observations in five areas: risk assessment methodologies, prediction approaches, key data, regulatory process and linkages. The case study indicated that reliance on predictive sensitization data from healthy volunteers generated unrealistically high no/low effect levels, while epidemiological surveillance and patient-based threshold data ultimately proved decisive, informing EU restrictions that led to declining sensitization rates. Read across approaches and chemical alert analyses show potential for earlier prevention, but their application has been inconsistent. Quantitative risk assessment remains limited by unresolved issues such as safety factors, aggregate exposure, and mixture effects. Strengthening transparency, integrating clinical evidence earlier, and improving regulatory coordination are essential to prevent future sensitization epidemics.

1 | Introduction

More than one quarter of the European population is sensitized to at least one chemical allergen, with fragrance ingredients and preservatives among the most frequent causative agents [1] and cosmetic products representing a major exposure source [2]. EU cosmetic regulation was first introduced in 1976 as a Directive [3]

and has since undergone extensive revision and now includes annexes listing banned, restricted, and permitted substances. In 1993 full ingredient labelling was introduced, but fragrance ingredients were initially exempted. This changed in 2003, when 26 fragrance allergens were identified which required labelling above 0.001% in leave-on and 0.01% in rinse-off products, fully implemented in 2005 [4]. In the same amendment, an out-phasing of animal

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testing was introduced. The ban was completed in 2013 following a deadline set out in the original cosmetic regulation in 2009 [5]. With the transition from a directive to a regulation, the legislation became directly applicable across all Member States [5]. In 2023, an additional 56 fragrance allergens were added to the labelling list at the same thresholds [6].

The European Commission established a scientific committee in 1977 to provide expert opinions on scientific and technical issues related to cosmetic products and their ingredients (Commission Decision 78/45/EEC, 19 December 1977) [7]. Initially named the Scientific Committee on Cosmetology, it has maintained its role while undergoing several name changes and is now known as the Scientific Committee on Consumer Safety (SCCS). Composed of independent experts from diverse scientific fields, the SCCS issues scientific opinions and methodological guidance for cosmetic ingredient safety assessment. Its regularly updated Notes of Guidance, most recently revised in 2023 [8], incorporate alternative methods and mention new approaches for assessing skin sensitization. These opinions and guidance documents form a central basis for ensuring cosmetic product safety and shape the analysis in this case study.

Despite the regulatory and methodological advances, several cases illustrate persistent challenges in preventing cosmetic-related skin sensitization. The aim of this case study is to outline selected EU-level interventions targeting specific cosmetic ingredients, evaluate their impact on population sensitization, and identify key principles relevant for future regulatory practice.

2 | Methods

2.1 | Identification of Case Allergens

The allergens in this case study were identified through a search strategy of the European Commission's webpage on public health [9]. All the opinions containing the letters "sensi" in the listed titles ($n=21$) were considered for inclusion. Using the webpage's built-in search function searching "sensitisation only" and "sensitisation endpoint" resulted in two additional hits. The allergens were included if: (1) the opinion concerned skin sensitization, (2) the allergens in question were chemically defined, (3) clinical and epidemiological data of skin sensitization/allergic contact dermatitis was available before and after adoption of the opinion and (4) the opinions were published between 1995 and 2020 to allow for follow-up. Opinions were also included for allergens chemically closely related to those assessed, such as other isothiazolinones, provided that sufficient data on their skin-sensitizing properties were available. Opinions concerning methodology were excluded. In total, this resulted in 7 allergens covered in 17 opinions being selected as cases in this investigation.

Among the identified substances two, methylisothiazolinone (MI), a preservative, and hydroxyisohexyl 3-cyclohexene carboxaldehyde (HICC), a fragrance ingredient, were the subjects of most opinions and therefore formed the main cases of this investigation. Additionally, benzisothiazolinone (BIT), methyltribromo glutaronitrile (MDBGN), linalool and limonene, and 2-hydroxyethyl methacrylate (HEMA) were identified as secondary case stories.

2.2 | Analytical Approach

A targeted search was performed on peer-reviewed articles and regulatory texts (Amendments to the Cosmetic Regulation), for trends in contact allergy to the identified allergens with emphasis on multicentre studies preferably providing data before and after regulatory interventions. An overview of the toxicological tests used in the opinions was compiled with a specific focus on determining the types of data used for risk assessment, how risk assessment conclusions were derived and if this led to intervention that is, legislation (Table 1). The data on trends of contact allergy were used to analyse if SCCS opinions and legislation impacted/correlated with changes in the incidence/prevalence of contact allergy towards the substances (Table 1). The main findings from the analysis were summarized in Table 2.

3 | Case Stories

Methylchloroisothiazolinone/methylisothiazolinone (MCI/MI): In 1986, MCI/MI was accepted for use in cosmetic products as a preservative in the European Economic Community (EEC) at a concentration of 30 ppm in a 3:1 mixture [32]. Already in 1989 this was reduced to 15 ppm (Directive 89/174/EEC) [33], due to numerous cases of contact allergy to MCI/MI arising from cosmetic products [34].

3.1 | MI

In 1987, Bruze et al. performed a modified Guinea pig maximization test (GPMT) with the two substances MCI and MI. This experiment showed that MCI was a strong sensitizer whereas MI was a weaker sensitizer [35]. At the same time, the first cases were published where MI was shown to have sensitized some individuals who were also sensitized to MCI [36]. Following the previous use of MI in an MCI/MI formulation, MI was accepted as a stand-alone preservative for use in cosmetic products at a concentration of 100 ppm in 2005.

3.1.1 | Epidemiology

The first cases of allergic contact dermatitis towards MI as a stand-alone preservative reported in 2004 [37] were of occupational origin. Subsequently, reports of MI contact allergy with cosmetic products as the primary source, such as wet wipes and make-up removers, began to emerge in the early 2010's [38, 39]. The prevalence among patch tested patients continued to rise in Europe and peaked in 2013/2014 at 8.7% in European Surveillance System on Contact Allergies (ESSCA) and at 5.9% in Information Network of Departments of Dermatology (IVDK) [30].

3.1.2 | Causes

Before the 2010's, contact allergy to MI may have been influenced by cross reactions between MCI and MI. However, an increasing number of cases of MI contact allergy originating from products containing MI only were reported [40] and the prevalence of MI contact allergy increased rapidly in EU countries, with cosmetics

TABLE 1 | Non-exhaustive overview of opinions made regarding the chemicals investigated in this paper.

Substance, year, opinion	Sensitization										Elicitation			Core data forming the data conclusion	Legislation	Result	Comment
	Human maximization test		HRIPT	OET	Guinea pig maximization test	Draize test	Buchler	LLNA	PT	ROAT	Dose response patch test	Other					
	HR IPT	maximization test															
MI, 2003, 2004 SCCNFP/0625/02 [10] SCCNFP/0805/04 [11]	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x		HR IPT: 0/97 sensitized to 100ppm (5 µg/cm ²).	100 ppm allowed in all types of CP.	Epidemic of MI allergy.	No new skin sensitization data added from 02 to 04 opinion.	
MI, 2013, SCCS/1521/13 [12]	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x		Leave-on ROAT: reaction to 5 ppm: No safe dose found. Rinse-off: Comparison of permitted MCI/MI concentration (15 ppm in a mixture 3:1), where MCI is the most potent allergen.	MI banned in leave on products. No action concerning rinse off.	Decreasing MI allergy prevalences.		
MI, 2015, SCCS/1557/15 [13]	x						x	x	x				QRA: Results disregarded, as the predicted safe use levels for some product categories were very high. Shower gel predicted to safely contain 12000 ppm (1.2%).	Confirmation of the 2013 assessment. Limited to 15 ppm in rinse-off products.	Decreasing MI allergy prevalences.		
HICC, 1999, SCCNFP/0017/98 [14]								x					Prevalence of HICC contact allergy 2.8% in consecutive patch tested patients.	Labelling requirements.			
HICC, 2003, SCCNFP/0743/03 [15]								x	x	x	x		1.9%–2.7% of eczema patients had a positive patch test to HICC. Safe concentration based on elicitation doses from experiments (0.02%).	No action.	No change.	SCCNFP found that a concentration up to 0.02% (1 µg/cm ²) would have a low potential to induce sensitization and elicit reactions. Industry recommended 1.5%.	

(Continues)

TABLE 1 | (Continued)

Substance, year, opinion	Sensitization										Elicitation			Core data forming the data conclusion	Legislation	Result	Comment
	Human maximization test	HRIPT	OET	Guinea pig maximization test	Draize test	Buchler	LLNA	PT	ROAT	Use test/patch	Dose response test	Other	Core data forming the data conclusion				
HICC, 2004, SCCP/0838/04 [16]	x	x		x		x	x	x	x	x	x	x	The experimental induction data (animal and human) was disregarded as high doses were identified as no effect levels. These could not be considered a safe level. Prevalences of HICC allergy remained high.	No action. SCCP required data for all toxicological endpoints.	No change.	Submission on HICC from industry: a NOEL of 4000 µg/cm ² was suggested based on animal and human induction studies.	
HICC, 2011, SCCP/1456/11 [17]	x	x		x		x	x	x	x	x	x	x	Despite industry efforts (IFRA): no decline in sensitization by a voluntary 200 ppm limit for deodorants. Epidemiological data still showcasing high prevalences (around 2%).	No action.		IFRA standard 2009 for example, 0.02% for use in deodorants and 0.2% in all other cosmetic products except oral care. The SCCS concluded that HRIPT and maximization studies raise ethical concerns and have limited predictive value in this context.	
HICC, 2012, SCCS/1459/11 [18]						x	x	x	x				Despite industry efforts (IFRA): No decline in sensitization by a voluntary 200 ppm limit for deodorants. Epidemiological data still showcasing high prevalences (around 2%).	HICC banned with an implementation phase of 4 years.	Decreasing trend in HICC allergy prevalence.	QRA data submitted but largely disregarded. CLP: HICC added as sensitizer effective in 2018 [19].	

(Continues)

TABLE 1 | (Continued)

Substance, year, opinion	Sensitization										Elicitation				Core data forming the data conclusion	Legislation	Result	Comment
	Human maximization test					Guinea pig maximization test					Dose response patch test							
	HR IPT	OET	Buchler	LLNA	PT	ROAT	Use test/ROAT	Dose response patch test	Other									
BIT, 2004, SCCNFP/0811/04 [20]	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x				Concluded to be a moderate sensitizer based on experimental data.	Not possible to conclude.		Lacking information in other toxicological endpoints. Concluded to be a moderate sensitizer.	
BIT, 2012, SCCS/1482/12 [21]	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x				Sensitization from isothiazolinones is a problem in consumers. Bit is a skin sensitizer with potency similar to MI. MI at 100 ppm is causing allergy. Patch tests from patients sensitized to gloves	Not accepted for cosmetics.		Other: Sensitization seen from gloves at 20ppm.	
MDBGN, 2002, SCCNFP/0585/02 [22]										x				Patch test data: increase from 0.7% positives in 1991 to 3.5% in 2000 from 11 countries and similar data from UK.	Banned in leave-on cosmetics (2005).	See below.		
MDBGN, 2005, SCCP/0863/05 [23]										x				ROAT in allergic patients with a rinse-off product at 0.1% elicited a reaction in 9/27 (37%).	Ban from rinse off products 2007.	Decrease in allergy prevalence.	The SCCP drew the attention of the Commission to the risks from other types of consumer products and that MDBGN had not yet been classified as a skin sensitizer.	

(Continues)

TABLE 1 | (Continued)

Substance, year, opinion	Sensitization						Elicitation			Core data forming the data conclusion	Legislation	Result	Comment			
	Human maximization test	HRIPT	OET	Guinea pig maximization test	Draize test	Buchler	LLNA	PT	ROAT					Dose response patch test	Use test/	Other
MDBGN, 2006, SCCP/1013/06 [24]			x				x	x				The use tests included were disregarded as several methodical aspects were lacking blinding, control group, too low frequency of application and too few subjects.	Not allowed for cosmetics.		CLP: classified as a skin sensitizer effective in 2027 [25].	
Linalool and limonene, 1999, SCCNFP/0017/98 [26]							x					Cases of allergy towards linalool were reported. Limonene prevalences range 0.9% positive to 2.6%.	Labelling requirements.	Linalool and Limonene Increasingly frequent positive patch test prevalences.	Part of a general opinion regarding fragrance allergens.	
Linalool and limonene, 2012, SCCS/1459/11 [18]						x	x					Prevalences at 2% positive patch tests and above.	No additional action regarding linalool and limonene.	Linalool and Limonene Increasingly frequent positive patch test prevalences.	Part of a general opinion regarding fragrance allergens.	
HEMA, SCCS/1592/17, 2018 [27]				x			x	x			x	Nail penetration: comparison of permeability studies from other similarly sized chemicals. Multiple studies showing allergy in both professional use and from consumers.	For professional use only.	Ongoing and increasing problem with HEMA allergy.	Opinion emphasizes that the nail plate is a sufficient barrier of protection. Other: Freuds complete adjuvant test. CLP: HEMA added as sensitizer effective in 2019 [28].	

Note: Tests used in the opinions are divided into either sensitization or elicitation studies. Where possible if the opinion led to a legislation this is noted and the apparent consequence of the prevalence in contact allergy is given. Abbreviations: CLP: Regulation (EC) No 1272/2008 on classification labelling and packaging; HRIPT: Human Repeat Insult Patch Test; LLNA: local Lymph Node Assay; NAM: New Approach Methods; OET: Open Epicutaneous Test; PT: Patch Test; ROAT: Repeat Open Application Test.

being the dominant source, whereas sensitization from industrial products such as paint, glues, and other exposures was low during those years [2, 31, 41]. Approx. 10% of MI sensitized patients reported to experience airborne contact dermatitis after having spent time in a newly painted room, and some also reported rhinitis and/or asthma [2, 31, 42]. In Australia, likewise, exposure to MI was in 2014 suspected to mainly originate from cosmetics while 8% were of occupational origin [43].

3.1.3 | Intervention

Rising rates of MI contact allergy led the SCCS in 2013 to conclude that no safe level of MI could be established for leave-on products (SCCS/1521/13) [12]. The same conclusion was reached in 2015 [44], after additional data received from industry, resulting in an EU ban on MI in leave-on products, including wet wipes (Regulation (EU) 2016/1198 [45]) (effective in 2017). In 2017, MI in rinse-off products was further restricted to 0.0015% (15 ppm), effective in 2018 [46].

Sensitization rates in the EU began declining around the 2015 opinion (Figure 1), likely aided by increased media attention and subsequent presumed decrease in use from industry/manufacturers. European Surveillance System on Contact Allergies (ESSCA) data show MI allergy peaking in 2013/2014, then falling after 2014/2015, reaching 2.9% in 2022 [30].

Canada implemented the same ban and restrictions in 2018, with the prevalence dropping from 15.2% to 12.7% between 2017/2018 and 2019/2020 [48, 49]. Australia banned MI in leave-on products in October 2017, reducing positive patch tests from 20.3% in 2015 to 11.4% in 2017; [43] no recent data are available. In New Zealand, MI allergy peaked at 12% in 2017, with subsequent declines attributed to international tightening of concentration limits [47]. In the United States, where MI remains unregulated, prevalence continued to rise (Figure 1).

3.1.4 | Risk Assessment and Management Methodologies

The 2003 Scientific Committee on Cosmetic Products and Non-Food Products (SCCNFP) opinion allowing 100ppm MI in all cosmetic products was based on animal studies and human induction experiments, for example, Human Repeated Insult Patch Tests (HRIPT) (Table 1), many of which were industry in-house data not publicly available. A few peer-reviewed studies on patch-tested patients, focusing on MI reactivity in individuals sensitized to MCI/MI, were also included. The SCCNFP concluded that HRIPT data suggested a low risk of new sensitizations at 100ppm MI. Three HRIPTs with 97 to 100 healthy subjects exposed repeatedly to 100 to 300ppm MI produced zero reactors. They noted, however, that previously sensitized MCI/MI patients might still react to 100ppm MI, though numbers were expected to be low. Induction doses were 5–15 μg MI/cm² per application. No conversion to real-life exposure and no safety factors were applied [10].

Reassessment by the SCCS beginning in 2013 focused on epidemiological data from real-life exposure, high-risk products,

and elicitation thresholds, including simulated-use studies. It was concluded that 100ppm MI in cosmetics was not safe; for leave-on products (including wet wipes), no safe concentration for preventing induction or elicitation of allergy had been demonstrated. For rinse-off products, MI was considered safe at 15 ppm, matching the permitted MCI/MI level, with MCI being the stronger sensitizer [12].

In 2015, the SCCS issued a third opinion on MI in rinse-off and leave-on hair products, based on new industry data including Quantitative Risk Assessment (QRA) modelling and aggregate exposure estimates. The QRA predicted that 1.2% MI in shower gel, 0.18% in shampoo, and 300ppm in hairstyling products would not induce sensitization. This was before accounting for aggregate exposure. Calculations used a No expected sensitization induction level (NESIL) of 15 $\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$ and a safety factor of 100. The SCCNFP concluded that the fact that the QRA model permits such high levels of a strong sensitizer in rinse-off products seriously questioned its predictions and undermined the confidence in the presented QRA models [44].

3.2 | Other Preservatives

Preservatives require European Commission approval before cosmetic use. BIT was assessed by the SCCNFP (2004) and SCCS (2012). In 2004 it was judged to have lower sensitizing potency than other preservatives based on Local Lymph Node Assay (LLNA) data but was not approved due to gaps in toxicological data beyond skin sensitization [20]. In 2014 the SCCS concluded BIT could not be considered safe because no safe exposure level for skin sensitization could be established, relying partly on read-across from the MCI/MI and MI epidemics in the EU [21].

MDBGN was permitted in cosmetics after a favourable 1986 opinion from the Scientific Committee of Cosmetology (SCC) [50], predecessor of the SCCS [22], which stated—without detail—that 0.3% was not sensitizing. MDBGN was later shown to be a strong sensitizer, with rising contact allergy rates (Table 1). Between 2002 and 2006, several SCCP assessments found no evidence for a safe level. In 2002 MDBGN was recommended only for rinse-off products due to higher exposure from leave-on formulations [22]. In 2005 it was shown to elicit reactions even at the allowed 0.1% in rinse-off products, leading to the conclusion that no safe use level existed for either leave-on or rinse-off cosmetics. It was recommended that MDBGN should not be present in any cosmetic products [23]. Rates of positive patch tests declined thereafter, though many unexplained positives remained [51]. In this context, it is important to note that the SCCS also expressed concern about widespread non-cosmetic uses of MDBGN [23]. Concerns have been raised that renewed industry interest and limited disclosure could trigger another rise in sensitization outside cosmetic use [52].

3.3 | HICC

HICC (Lyril) is a synthetic fragrance allergen that was unregulated and unrestricted in the international fragrance

association (IFRA) standards until a 1997/98 EU-funded multicentre study identified it as a frequent and significant allergen [53]. It was subsequently added to the diagnostic Fragrance Mix (FM) II [54].

3.3.1 | Epidemiology

A multicentre study reported HICC positivity in 2.7% of 1855 European patients (range 1.2%–17%), second only to FM I at 11.3% [55]. Numerous later studies confirmed these findings and were summarized in the 2003 opinion [15]. In 2008, HICC 5% was added to the European Baseline Series as a core allergen [56].

3.3.2 | Causes

Studies in the 1990s showed HICC was widely present in cosmetics [57]. Among HICC-positive patients, 64% had a certain or probable history of fragrance-related symptoms from cosmetic use [55]. Case reports linked allergic dermatitis to specific cosmetic products via patch testing and chemical analysis; one prestige eau de toilette contained 2.3% HICC, while other products contained <1% [58]. Deodorants were a major concern, with HICC detected in 53% of products at concentrations up to 0.18% [57].

From 2002 to 2011, cosmetics were the probable cause in 39.9% of HICC-related dermatitis cases, while occupational exposure accounted for 15.1% [59]. A 2007 Danish study found HICC in 72% of tested cosmetics (mainly eau de parfum and eau de toilette) [58], and a UK study the same year found 29% of cosmetic and household products labelled with HICC [60]. Danish data from 2003 to 2011 showed a stable HICC allergy prevalence of ~2.5% in patch-tested patients [61]. In the general population, the EDEN study found a prevalence of 1.4% [1].

3.3.3 | Intervention

HICC was among the 26 fragrances requiring labelling above 0.001% in leave-on and 0.01% in rinse-off products following a 1999 opinion [4]. In 2003, IFRA set a 1.5% maximum for HICC, while the SCCNFP recommended a far lower safe limit of 0.02%, but neither the 2003 nor 2004 opinions resulted in regulation. IFRA introduced a QRA-based standard in 2008, but due to persistently high HICC allergy rates, further restricted HICC to 0.02% in deodorants, lip and intimate wipe products in 2009 (SCCS/1459/11 Tables 11–7) [18].

A 2011 SCCS review concluded that industry efforts since 2003 had failed to curb the HICC allergy epidemic and that no safe exposure level could be identified. In the SCCS's 2012 general opinion on fragrance allergens (SCCS/1459/11) [18], HICC was designated a major allergen of concern and was added to Annex II of the Cosmetics Regulation in 2017, resulting in a full ban with a four-year implementation period [62].

From 2009 to 2019, Denmark showed an annual decrease of 0.156% points in HICC contact allergy, with a smaller decline observed in ESSCA data [63]. In Italy, a modest downward trend was reported, with prevalence around 1% from 2016 to 2021 [64].

3.3.4 | Risk Assessment and Management Methodologies

The 2003 opinion was triggered by public health concerns, linking epidemiological patch-test data to specific HICC exposures in cosmetic products [15]. It was concluded that existing HICC levels were unsafe. Dose response patch test thresholds (0.9–10 µg/cm²), modelled using QRA principles, led to a recommended maximum of 0.02% of HICC in cosmetics (SCCNFP 2003), expected to keep sensitization and elicitation low.

FIGURE 1 | Prevalence of MI allergy over time. Data from multiple articles incorporated into a single graph. The data from ESSCA, IVDK and NACDG [30] was aggregated in the years 2009–2010, 2011–2012, 2013–2014, 2015–2016 and 2017–2018. Data from Australia [43] and New Zealand [47] had a 1-year period. Additional data from 2009 and 2012 from IVDK is also visualized [41]. Abbreviations: SCCS: Scientific Committee on Consumer Safety, ESSCA: European Surveillance System on Contact Allergies, IVDK: Information Network of Departments of Dermatology, NACDG: North American Contact Dermatitis Group.

TABLE 2 | Observations from the case studies regarding future needs in regulatory prevention.

Observation	Example	Future needs	Key references
Risk assessment methods/models			
Risk assessment process did not incorporate current key knowledge of risk drivers.	MI: not used dose/area or adjustment factors in risk assessment.	A generally accepted risk assessment model needs to be developed.	MI, 2003, SCCNFP/0625/02 [10].
Several elements in the QRA model lack a critical and updated scientific review.	Safety factors, mixture effects and so forth, do not incorporate latest knowledge.	Systematic reviews of current knowledge warranted to support relevant changes.	HICC, 2012, SCCS/1459/11 [18]. MI, 2015 SCCS/1557/15 [13].
Old data from predictive models is repeatedly used as benchmarks in the QRA.	HICC predictive tests dating back to 1958 are used in submissions.	Clinical data should take precedence if a problem has been identified in the population at risk. New more sophisticated predictive assays are needed to advance this field and exploit development in immunology	Memorandum [29]. SCCP/1456/11 [17].
Employed unfinished, unvalidated risk assessment models	MI; HICC	A generally accepted risk assessment model needs to be developed.	HICC: 2012, SCCS/1459/11 [18] and 2003, SCCNFP/0743/03 [15]. MI, 2015, SCCS/1557/15 [13].
Widespread exposures from multiple products may cause significant problems.	Models do not take this sufficiently into account: MI; HICC	Correction for aggregate exposures: should be revisited.	HICC: 2012, SCCS/1459/11 [18]. 2015, SCCS/1557/15 [13].
Predictions			
Chemical alerts	Not considered	Should be a formal part of the risk assessment.	SCCNFP/0625/02 [10].
Read across	BIT not allowed in cosmetics as it has similarities with MI/MCI already causing problems.	Group assessment with mutual decisions as part of a tiered approach.	BIT, 2012, SCCS/1482/12 [21].
Key data			
Epidemiological data demonstrating disease from actual exposures ignored, leading to continued problems.	HICC: no effect elicitation levels from patients replaced with up to 4000 higher doses derived from predictive induction tests.	Precedence of clinical data over predictive tests	Memorandum [29].
Overemphasis on experimental models (animals; humans) using in-house data of unknown quality	MI; HICC	Poor predictability in some cases. Raw data should be available for scrutiny, if not published peer reviewed.	MI: 2003 SCCNFP/0625/02 [10] and 2004 SCCNFP/0805/04 [11]. HICC, 2004, SCCP/0838/04 [16].
Surveillance data of contact allergy cases has pinpointed new allergens of concern, identified risk products and offered solutions.	MI, HICC etc.	A European Surveillance system of contact allergy should be supported and linked to decisions.	ESSCA [30, 31].

(Continues)

TABLE 2 | (Continued)

Observation	Example	Future needs	Key references
Process			
Long delays in decisions due to repeated submissions	HICC: 18 years from first submission to final implementation	Deadlines	HICC, 1999, SCCNFP/0017/98 [14].
Linkage of regulations			
A substance may be banned in cosmetic products but still not classified as an allergen under REACH	MDBGN: decision of ban in 2005; classified as sensitizer in 2025	Linked processes	MDBGN, 2005 ban [23]. Classified as sensitizer in 2025 [25].

No regulation followed because industry submitted additional in-house LLNA and HRIPT data proposing a much higher No Observed Effect Level (NOEL) focused solely on risk of induction giving a NOEL around 4000 µg/cm², that is, 400–4000 times higher than the NOEL (thresholds) applied in the 2003 opinion. The SCCS (2004) emphasized that epidemiological data clearly showed HICC allergy was a significant European problem, and that experimental induction data had poor predictive value in this particular case [65].

In 2008 IFRA issued a new QRA-based standard for 11 product categories, and in 2009 reduced the concentration limit for deodorants and lip products to 0.02% (2011 opinion table) [18]. The SCCS's 2011 HICC-specific opinion again focused on human and epidemiological evidence, concluding that no safe use level could be identified due to persistently high prevalence rates [66]. The 2012 general fragrance-allergy opinion (SCCS/1459/11) reaffirmed that HICC should not be used in consumer products, as high sensitization rates persisted even after the 0.02% and 0.2% limits were introduced by IFRA, depending on the product category [18].

3.4 | Linalool and Limonene

The pre-haptens linalool and limonene were included in the list of 26 fragrance allergens with mandatory labelling in effect in 2009 [5]. Despite the long-lasting risk management attempt (labelling) the prevalence rate for the oxidized linalool and d-limonene is ranging from 0.83% to 11.7% (20% found in a smaller study with 103 participants) and 1.3% to 8%, respectively [67]. No new initiatives have been taken to limit this.

3.5 | HEMA

HEMA has long been recognized as a sensitizer, historically linked to occupational exposure among dental personnel, painters, printers, and workers handling adhesives. Currently, its use in nail cosmetics has driven a marked increase in contact allergy [68]. In 2018, the SCCS classified HEMA (and Di-HEMA) as weak to moderate sensitizers, concluding that sensitization likely results from accidental exposure outside the nail plate, as penetration here is negligible. Consequently, HEMA was added to Annex III of the Cosmetics Regulation in 2020, requiring product labels to state

“for professional use only” and “can cause an allergic reaction” [69]. Multiple studies have shown that this regulation has not had any detectable effect in reversing the increase in HEMA allergy, that is largely driven by nail products [70].

4 | Discussion

The case story of MI, being a strong sensitizer allowed in high concentrations in all cosmetic products, illustrates how inadequate safety assessment can lead to widespread public health issues given the frequent, daily, and multi-product exposure typical of preservatives and fragrances in cosmetic products. These early assessments were grounded in the methodological conventions of their time; however, they did not incorporate emerging evidence indicating that risk is governed by dose per unit area rather than concentration alone. However later, the QRA approach (2015) introduced the concept of threshold dose in µg/cm², but still predicted that 100 ppm MI could be safely used in many products and at even higher levels for example 1800 ppm in hairstyling products, than had been allowed (SCCS 2015). At this point MI allergy was a large problem in EU and these findings highlighted important limitations and unresolved uncertainties in the QRA methodology [44]. Although QRA has since evolved and a simplified version was recently published [71], the model remains unapproved by SCCS and lacks updated critical review of central elements such as safety factors, aggregate exposure and mixture effects. Recently, the statistical model SARA-ICE has been included in the OECD guideline 497 [72]. The model provides ED01, an estimate of the dermal dose, which will induce sensitization in 1% of the population exposed in a Human Repeated Insult Patch Test (HRIPT) to be used as a point of departure in risk assessment [72, 73].

4.1 | Key Data in Risk Assessment

The case stories of MI and HICC show that epidemiological surveillance for contact allergy and experimental data from sensitized patients were central in guiding the need for and type of intervention on an EU level. Reduced prevalences of skin sensitization for MI, particularly in EU countries, followed (Figure 1), and an effect for HICC was also seen. A secondary, delayed spill-over effect due to stricter concentration limits internationally

may also, to some extent, have reduced sensitization rates in countries without regulations [47].

In the cases studied, epidemiological evidence documenting a substantial real-world disease burden has, in several cases, been given less weight in regulatory submissions than experimental induction studies in animals and healthy volunteers. These induction studies typically report no-effect levels that were substantially higher than thresholds derived from patient-based and epidemiological data. For instance, in the case of HICC, patient-based data identified elicitation thresholds in the range of 1–10 $\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$, whereas induction studies in healthy volunteers (HRIPT) reported no-effect levels around 4000 $\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$. Applying the latter values in QRA would, in principle, allow permitted concentrations substantially higher than those observed in marketed products [57]. A substantial reliance on unpublished, historical in-house data (e.g., HICC benchmarks from 1958) and un-validated models further delays effective risk management, in the case of HICC for 18 years [14, 18]. Higher levels of data transparency are needed to allow public independent quality assurance and more advanced and sensitive predictive immunological assays to strengthen safety assessments. Surveillance data are essential for monitoring trends, identifying emerging risks, and evaluating the impact of interventions, including regulatory measures. Traditionally, such data have been generated through national and international networks of dermatologists who systematically collect and analyse patch test results. The European Surveillance System on Contact Allergies has been particularly valuable in identifying emerging allergens, characterizing exposure patterns, and assessing the effectiveness of regulatory actions [30, 31]. This or similar European systems should be supported and integrated with regulatory frameworks to establish a sustained and responsive feedback loop, enhancing effective prevention.

4.2 | Read Across

In the opinion 02/04 permitting MI in cosmetic products the knowledge of MCI/MI was only included to a limited extent. In contrast in the case of BIT, a read-across approach was employed, as learning for the MI epidemic influenced decision on BIT, which was not allowed in cosmetic products, due to chemical similarities. As thousands of chemicals have been identified as skin sensitizers, read-across approaches could give more effective preventive actions and save resources. The case of HICC shows that its sensitizing properties could have been identified earlier, as chemical alerts show similarities with hydroxycitronellal, another well-known fragrance allergen. However, such analyses were rarely applied previously [74]. The methods currently available are not robust enough to allow stand-alone decision making. Read-across has the potential to be a powerful screening and prioritization tool, but it is best used as part of a tiered approach that could trigger additional testing if alerts are shown.

4.3 | Ingredient Labelling as Preventive Tool

Ingredient labelling on cosmetic products is a critical measure for diagnosing allergic contact dermatitis and providing

secondary or tertiary protection for sensitized individuals [75]. All ingredients must be listed individually on cosmetic products, except fragrances, where Annex III specifies a list of fragrance allergens that must be declared above certain concentrations. This information can be complex, and patients and clinicians struggle to use it effectively, depending on the allergen [76, 77]. Historically, patients allergic to formaldehyde faced challenges because it was only declared at very high concentrations, despite its widespread presence in formaldehyde-releasing compounds [76]. A recent regulatory adjustment lowered the threshold for formaldehyde labelling to 10 ppm, based on clinical observations and Repeat Open Application (ROAT) experiments in sensitized individuals [78], improving the situation for formaldehyde sensitized consumers significantly. Labelling of individual fragrance allergens has also been shown to assist patients in identifying scented products that they can tolerate [79].

For HEMA, regulators attempted to prevent sensitization by requiring labels stating “for professional use only” on products containing HEMA or Di-HEMA. However, these products remain accessible to consumers, and the effectiveness of this warning is unclear, as the prevalence of HEMA contact allergy is still rising [68, 70], indicating the need for another type of intervention.

4.4 | Linkage of Regulations

MDBGN was banned from use in cosmetic leave-on products in 2005 [80] and in 2007 for rinse-off products [81]. However, MDBGN did not receive harmonized classification as a skin sensitizer until April 2025 (effective 2027) [25]; before this, only 57% of MDBGN-containing articles were self-classified as sensitizers [52]. This means that there for many years has been a hidden exposure to this allergen hampering prevention. In the MDBGN 2005 opinion, it was stated that the risks to consumer health from the presence of MDBGN in other types of consumer products with relevant skin contact should be assessed. The attention of the Commission was drawn to this; however, no action was taken probably as no standard procedures have been established in the Commission to handle this. Data and decisions should be shared routinely between regulatory areas.

5 | Conclusion

The cases examined demonstrate the need for stronger primary prevention to protect European consumers from cosmetic-induced skin sensitization. Prolonged outbreaks, including the MI and HICC epidemics, arose from delayed or insufficient risk assessment and regulatory action. A widely accepted, routinely applicable (quantitative) risk assessment model for skin sensitization is required, incorporating updated knowledge on safety factors, aggregate exposure, and mixture effects, as noted by the SCCS. Early integration of emerging clinical evidence is essential to prevent widespread sensitization and enable timely intervention. In case of epidemics the key data would be derived from sensitized patients. Improved transparency in industry data, including access to raw datasets, and more effective information exchange across regulatory domains are critical to achieving effective prevention.

Author Contributions

Jose Hernán Alfonso: conceptualization, writing – review and editing. **Christina Rudén:** conceptualization, writing – review and editing. **Steen Mollerup:** conceptualization, writing – review and editing. **Jeanne Duus Johansen:** conceptualization, writing – original draft, writing – review and editing, methodology, investigation, supervision, project administration, formal analysis. **Jakob Ferløv Baselius Schwensen:** conceptualization, methodology, investigation, writing – review and editing, supervision. **Gianluca Selvestrel:** conceptualization, writing – review and editing. **Mathias Krogh Pedersen:** conceptualization, investigation, writing – original draft, methodology, visualization, writing – review and editing, project administration, formal analysis. **Martin F. Wilks:** conceptualization, writing – review and editing.

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Conflicts of Interest

Jakob Ferløv Baselius Schwensen has served as investigator for Sanofi. Jose Hernán Alfonso received an unrestricted research grant from Sanofi. Received honoraria for presentations from Almirall, Sanofi, Essity, and Leo Pharma and as medical advisor for Novartis, Leo Pharma, and Takeda. Jeanne Duus Johansen has served as external expert to SCCNFP/SCCS concerning skin sensitization on an ad hoc basis.

Data Availability Statement

Data sharing not applicable to this article as no datasets were generated or analysed during the current study.

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